

LIFE-CYCLE INTERACTIONS FOR MODELLING HUMAN EMOTIONS

A FOUNDATION FOR DEVELOPING 'DESIGN FOR EMOTION' SUPPORT TOOLS

Jonathan C. Borg, Lawrence Farrugia
Concurrent Engineering Research Unit, University of Malta
✉ jonathan.borg@um.edu.mt, lawrence.farrugia.07@um.edu.mt

ABSTRACT

This paper presents a theoretical model representing human emotions as consequences of life-cycle interactions. Research into product design has been in the most part, limited to emotions elicited as a result of user-product interactions that take place during the use phase. Yet interactions involving humans, the artefact, and other life-phase systems span across the entire life cycle of the artefact. The study of emotions in product design should therefore be broadened by comprehensively considering and understanding the human interactions that occur across different life-phases. The implication is to consider human emotions, which result from the interactions involving the human worker, the artefact and other systems, as these take place throughout various life-cycle phases. The life-cycle interactions model, presented in this paper, establishes the foundation for the development and application of support tools, which take into consideration the influence of product design in eliciting emotions from human workers and customers.

KEYWORDS: *Meeting theory, life-phase systems, worker emotions, life-cycle consequences, CAD tools*

PROBLEM BACKGROUND

Research in product design and emotion has limited its focus on the study of emotions elicited as a result of the user-product interactions which take place during the use phase in the life-cycle of an artefact. In reality, the interactions between humans and the artefact are not exclusively limited to the use phase. Instead, throughout its life, the artefact interacts with multiple artificial and natural life-phase systems, where the latter includes human beings. It follows that human-product interactions take place throughout numerous life-cycle phases, which precede and follow the use phase. Some examples of interactions involving the artefact, the human worker, and other life-phase systems are: manual assembly of the evolving artefact during the manufacturing phase, the repair of a product during the servicing phase, and the disposal of a product by a human worker at the end of the artefact's life-cycle. These simple examples indicate that in order to understand the impact of product design on human emotions, one has to broaden the meaning of the term 'human-product interactions' in order to include both the end customer and life-phase human

workers. In this manner the understanding of emotions elicited as a result of human-product interactions will span across the entire life-cycle of the artefact.

Over the years, researchers have proposed numerous approaches that support designers in creating artefacts, which elicit positive emotions from the end customers, particularly during the use phase. Fenech and Borg proposed a phenomena model (Fenech & Borg, 2006a) of product emotion elicitation, which was subsequently used in the development of an approach (Fenech & Borg, 2006b), intended to provide design for emotion support. This approach was later implemented into a prototype design tool (Farrugia et al., 2008), which employs computer aided sketching in order to support the conceptual synthesis of a product form that elicits positive emotions.

A repertoire consisting of 25 emotion types (Desmet, 2012) was proposed due to the fact that previous emotion taxonomies were either too concise or extremely complex to be employed in design practice. In their research work, Fokkinga and Desmet (Fokkinga & Desmet, 2012; S. F. Fokkinga & Desmet, 2013) proposed a design approach whereby they demonstrated

how negative emotions can create emotionally rich product experiences for the users. In this paper the authors explain how under very specific conditions, people are willing to engage and enjoy activities which are known to elicit negative emotions, such as fear.

Ludden and Schifferstein (2009) investigated the influence of scents on the evaluation of a product by the end customer. A similar research work (Rahman, 2012) investigated the influence of visual and tactile stimuli on the end customer's evaluation of a pair of denim jeans. The investigation presented in this paper (Rahman, 2012) concluded that both visual and tactile stimuli can elicit sensations of different intensities, thus influencing the user's evaluation of the artefact.

The auditory sense is also a medium through which positive or negative emotions can be elicited. Fenko et al. (2011) investigated the impact of product noise on the user's experience. According to the authors, the definition of the term 'noise' should not be limited to the auditory property of a product; instead this term should include visual noise such as cluttered visual patterns. The study (Fenko et al., 2011) suggested that product noise resulting from visual patterns, had little influence on the participants' evaluation. On the contrary, the

auditory noise of a product had a negative influence on the overall pleasantness of the product as perceived by the evaluators. In view of these results, the research in this paper (Fenko et al., 2011) concludes that designers need to take into consideration the auditory characteristics of the product as this can influence its evaluation by the end customer.

The above state-of-the-art review pertaining to design and emotion, exclusively takes into account the emotions elicited by a product as a result of the interactions taking place during the use phase. Yet the use phase represents only one instance of the many phases in the life-cycle of a product (Olesen, 1992). Each life-phase may involve the interaction between the artefact, which exists in a certain state, the human being, and other life-phase systems, as illustrated in Figure 1.

The emphasis of this research, is that human emotions are not elicited exclusively from the human customer, but also from the life-phase worker_X, where 'X' corresponds to a distinct life-phase (1), (2), (3) and (4) shown in Figure 1. Research into product design and emotions should therefore extend to other life-cycle phases in order to include the emotions of human workers who interact with the evolving artefact throughout life-phases, which precede and follow the use phase.

Figure 1. Human interactions and the elicited emotions across the entire life-cycle of the artefact

The objective of this paper is to present a theoretical model for the emotion elicitation of both human workers and users, which stem as a consequence of life-phase interactions. The next section will provide a brief overview of the process involved in the elicitation of a human emotion and its influence on other aspects, such as physiology and behavior. The literature in this section will also outline why the knowledge pertaining to the elicitation of worker emotions is of relevance to the industry, thus providing a justification for the applicability of the model presented in this paper.

The third section of this paper will present the original theoretical model that has been adapted for the purpose of this research. The fourth section will present in detail the model for human emotions in life-cycle interactions, which is the main contribution of this research. This model presents human emotions as a result of interactions involving the artefact and some natural and/or artificial life-phase systems, as illustrated in Figure 1. During the manufacturing phase (1) a human worker executes the expected tasks by interacting with the evolving artefact and a life-phase system such as a drill press. The model portrays worker emotions as one of the consequences that stem from the interactions involving the worker, the artefact, and other life-phase systems. The value of making the knowledge embodied in this model explicit is that it would enable product designers to take into consideration the influence that product design commitments have on the emotions elicited from life-phase workers who interact with the evolving artefact and other life-phase systems.

This model is then used in the fifth section in order to provide a rationale for the results obtained from an investigation into worker emotions. A discussion pertaining to the results obtained from this study will be presented within the same section. The main conclusions of this research, together with the limitations and further work, are presented in the last section of the paper.

THE APPRAISAL PROCESS IN HUMAN EMOTIONS

The study of human emotions is a vast and growing area of research, particularly in the field of psychology. It has only been in recent years that researchers have started to understand and propose theories regarding the process pertaining to the elicitation of emotions in human beings. One of the most accepted and proven theories, pioneered by Richard Lazarus (2006; Lazarus, & Folkman, 1984), is called appraisal theory. According to Lazarus (2006) an emotion is the result of an appraisal/evaluation of the impact of a stimulus to one's own concerns. Scherer et al. (2001) propose the idea that specific appraisals elicit distinct emotions. Thus, for example, while an unexpected and motive consistent stimulus results in the elicitation of hope, an unexpected and motive inconsistent stimulus results in the elicitation of fear.

The appraisal process is only one aspect of an emotion prototype (Russell, 2009). This is due to the fact that an emotional event brings about a number of changes such as, bodily

changes (Russell, 2003), including changes in physiology (Michie, 2002; Scherer et al., 2001); vocal and facial expressions, together with changes in perception (Fokkinga & Desmet, 2012); attitude (Fokkinga & Desmet, 2012); and behavior (Michie, 2002; Yang & Diefendorff, 2009).

Yang and Diefendorff (Yang & Diefendorff, 2009) examined a theoretical model (Spector & Fox, 2002) originally proposed by Spector and Fox (2002). The principle idea behind this theoretical model (Spector & Fox, 2002) is that negative emotions elicited by environmental stimuli render individuals more susceptible to engage in counter-productive work behavior (CWB); both towards people within the organization and/or the organization itself. This costly CWB is engaged, sometimes unconsciously, with the intent to reduce negative emotions. The result of the investigation (Yang & Diefendorff, 2009) was in support of this theory.

Other studies (Chang & Lu, 2007; Imtiaz & Ahmad, n.d.; Jo, 1992) have investigated the impact that stimuli such as the spatial configuration (Michie, 2002), temperature (Jo, 1992), work overload (Qureshi et al.), and other characteristics pertaining to the work environment have on worker emotions and their behavior as a consequence.

The research presented in this section indicates that the elicitation of negative emotions from the life-phase worker, can result in costs being incurred as a result of reduced productivity, increase in absenteeism, and slower product development. This indicates that there are tangible and valuable benefits to industry in making knowledge concerning life-phase interactions, involving the human worker and the elicited emotions, explicit.

THE ARTEFACT AND LIFE-PHASE SYSTEM INTERACTIONS

During each distinct phase of its life, the artefact interacts/meets with a number of life-phase systems (Borg, 1999) such as the fabrication, assembly, and inspection systems during the manufacturing phase, and the disposal system during the disposal phase. The systems, with which the artefact meets, can be classified as being natural or artificial, as shown in Figure 2.

Material handling equipment, such as fork lifters and fabrication machinery, such as a drill press, are all examples of artificial life-phase systems, while the human being and the natural environment are instances of natural life-phase systems. While interacting with these life-phase systems the artefact, or rather some of its properties, are transformed from one state to another (Hubka & Eder, 1988). The type of transformation that takes place depends on the previous state of the artefact and the life-phase systems involved in the interaction (Borg, 1999)

The illustration in Figure 3 shows the artefact during the manufacturing phase (1) of its life. Throughout this particular phase, the artefact changes its state as a result of the interaction with other life-phase systems. Thus during fabrication (A),

the artefact changes its physical state from unperforated to perforated by interacting with an artificial life-phase system called a drill press. In a similar fashion, during assembly (B), the artefact interacts with an assembly system consisting of an industrial robot, which changes the state of the artefact from unassembled to assembled. Similarly, during inspection (C) the artefact interacts with an inspection system that identifies any potential fabrication and assembly defects. Following inspection the artefact changes its state from un-inspected to inspected.

HUMAN EMOTIONS IN LIFE-CYCLE INTERACTIONS (HELCI)

The meeting concept presented in the preceding section revolves around the notion that the artefact meets with various natural and artificial systems throughout its entire life. The changes which the artefact experiences depend on the previous state of the artefact and the attributes of the life-phase systems involved in the interaction. Apart from the artificial systems shown in Figure 3, the life-phase interactions involve the participation of human life-phase workers who contribute in changing the state of the artefact.

The diagram in Figure 4 illustrates the meeting/interaction involving the artefact, two artificial life-phase systems, and the human worker_M during the manufacturing phase. The human worker_M and the drill press interact with the artefact in state 'i', in the context of an artificial work environment. The interaction results in the transformation of the artefact from state 'i' to state 'i+1'. In addition, this interaction produces consequences including the generation of noise and waste. It should be noted that the type of consequences, and their respective attributes, depend on the properties of

the artefact and the life-phase systems involved in the interaction. For example, if during the manufacturing phase the artefact material is recyclable then the waste which is generated as a consequence of the manufacturing phase interaction may also be recycled.

The novelty of the model presented, is that an additional consequence that stems from the interaction involving the human worker, the evolving artefact, and other life-phase systems, is the elicitation of emotions. Like other consequences, such as the generation of waste, the emotions elicited depend upon the attributes of both the artefact and the other life-phase systems involved in the interaction.

In the context of the example shown in Figure 4, the change in the emotional state of the worker_M is in part determined by the properties of the artefact and life-phase systems involved. If the worker_M interacts with a drill press which is unreliable, then this interaction will result in a progressive change in the emotional state of worker_M from happy to angry. In a similar fashion, if the life-phase worker_M is performing tasks within a factory that is uncomfortable with inappropriate lighting, then these properties of the work environment will also contribute to a change in the emotional state of the human life-phase worker_M.

The concept behind this model may be extended to other phases in the life of an evolving artefact as illustrated in Figure 5. Each phase 'X' in the life cycle of an artefact involves the interaction between the life-phase worker_X, the artefact, and possibly some other natural and/or artificial life-phase system. These interactions will result in an intended change in the state of the artefact, together with a number of consequences, such as the generation of waste, noise, and pollutants. The emphasis of the HELCI model is that life-phase interactions will also produce a change in the emotional state

Figure 2. A classification of life-phase systems

Figure 3. The evolving artefact during the manufacturing phase

Figure 4. Worker emotions elicited as a consequence of manufacturing life-phase interactions

of the life-phase worker_X. For example, during the transport phase the use of reliable and efficient material handling equipment within a safe work environment contributes in changing the emotional state of worker_T from sad to happy. Similarly, during the disposal phase, the worker_D may become gradually sad due to work being performed using dangerous and hazardous equipment.

This section presented a model of human emotions in life-cycle interactions (HELCI), which portrays the change in the emotional state of life-phase human workers and customers as a consequence of life-cycle interactions involving the artefact and other life-phase systems. The change in the emotional state of the human workers and customers depends on the properties of the artefact as well as the other life-phase systems involved in the interaction.

CASE STUDY - WORKER EMOTIONS IN VISUAL INSPECTION

Semi-structured interviews among six factory operators were carried out within a manufacturing company. All of the

participants in this semi-structured interview, were workers who interact in a direct manner with the artefact by conducting visual inspections on assembled artefacts. These inspections are executed in order to identify any scratches or other cosmetic defects. This task entails the use of magnification equipment and powerful light sources in order to render the cosmetic defects easily identifiable. The aim of the investigation was to determine if the theoretical HELCI model provides a rationale to the emotions elicited in a realistic scenario. In addition, the investigation would enable the research to identify the attributes pertaining to the artefact and the other life-phase systems which are considered to possess an emotional quality.

Key results

Throughout the semi-structured interviews the participants identified various attributes pertaining to the artefact and life-phase systems which were deemed to be responsible for the elicitation of emotions. Table 1 provides a list of attributes pertaining to product, work, or process that were considered by the participants to influence their emotional state.

Figure 5. Human emotions in life-cycle interactions (HELCI)

TABLE 1. A SUMMARY OF THE RESULTS OBTAINED

Attribute	Comment	Number of participants (Percentage %)
Excessive ambient noise levels in the work environment	The constant exposure to loud noises emanating from machinery can be tedious and frustrating.	5 (83)
Product colors	The color of the product can facilitate or impede the task of visual inspection.	5 (83)
Physical layout of workers	Workers not provided with ample working space feel frustrated, particularly if this state has to be sustained over an extended period of time. Another issue was the provision of chairs which do not offer proper lumbar support.	4 (67)
Layout of non-human elements e.g. machines and WIP	The cluttering of the factory floor which renders the physical environment: a. Unappealing b. Potentially hazardous c. Impractical to work in.	4 (67)
Illumination provided for the process	The illumination is a critical resource necessary to execute the task of visual inspection. Without appropriate illumination the task would be very difficult.	3 (50)
Tactile feeling	The subjects prefer a certain product because of its tactile feeling.	3 (50)

Table 1. A summary of the results obtained

The most frequently mentioned attributes were the excessive ambient noise of the work environment and the product colors. Both the physical layout of workers and the layout of work in progress (WIP) material, were two attributes of the work environment that were also considered by 67% of the interviewees to have a significant impact on their emotional state. In addition, the provision of proper illumination for inspection and the tactile feeling were also deemed to have some influence in eliciting worker emotions. It should be noted that apart from the results shown in Table 1, there were other desirable characteristics pertaining to the product and other artificial life-phase systems, which were identified by a minority of the workers to influence their emotional state. Such characteristics include the colors of the physical environment, the aesthetic appeal of the artefact, and the overall reliability of the machines and tools being used to execute the expected tasks.

Discussion

Based on the responses from the sample of participants, the results indicate that characteristics identified to have a capacity in eliciting worker emotions, can in fact be attributed to the properties of the artefact and other life-phases systems, such as the work environment. However, a more significant outcome that stems from the investigation is that the elicited emotions are a consequence of the meeting/interaction involving the human worker with the artefact and/or other life-phase systems. This implies that HELCI is a suitable theoretical model for describing life-cycle interactions as the basis of eliciting human emotions.

A human emotion is characterized by the evaluation of a stimulus/event in relation to one’s own concerns. This explains why certain attributes, pertaining to the artefact, process,

or the environment life-phase systems, were considered to have a higher degree of influence in eliciting emotions when compared to others. The illustration in Figure 6 provides a very good example of how the same attribute of the artefact, such as color, is appraised quite differently from the life-phase worker when compared to the user, thus eliciting contrasting emotions from both humans.

With reference to Figure 6, the life-phase worker and the customer interact with the artefact during distinct phases of the product’s life, which in this case are denoted by the manufacturing phase (1), and the use phase (2). The illustration in Figure 6 shows that the life-phase worker interacts with various properties of the artefact, one of which is color. Both the life-phase worker (3) and the end customer (4) are interacting with the same identical color, yet the same product attribute is appraised very differently. On one hand the appraisal of the life-phase worker results in the elicitation of negative emotions such as anger (5). This is due to the fact that the particular choice of color impedes the ability of the human worker to conduct the task of visual inspection, which is a major concern to the worker. On the other hand the end-customer appraises (6) the same identical product attribute in a more positive manner, thus eliciting more positively toned emotions. This is due to the fact that the concerns of the end-customer are significantly different from those of the life-phase worker. The major concern of the customer is to have a product that is aesthetically pleasing, and in the example shown in Figure 6 the choice of color is beneficial in relation to this particular concern.

In a similar manner the provision of appropriate lighting during the manufacturing phase, can determine the extent to which positive or negative emotions are elicited from the life-phase

Figure 6. The appraisal of artefact's color by the life-phase worker and the customer

worker. The presence or absence of this resource can significantly influence the degree of difficulty in identifying cosmetic defects. The same rationale explains why excessive ambient noise was considered to play a major role in eliciting negative worker emotions. This is due to the fact that the exposure to constant excessive noise can quite often be distracting, hence detrimental to the task at hand.

Another example of an attribute related to the work environment that was considered to elicit negative emotions was the organization of the physical factory floor, which in most part was cluttered with boxes filled with WIP. The interviewed subjects pointed out that this attribute of the physical work environment elicits negative emotions due to the fact that it renders the execution of tasks more difficult. Thus, apart from being visually unpleasant, the existence of a cluttered work environment poses a threat to the execution of tasks by rendering the physical work environment impractical to work in, as it renders the flow of material for inspection very difficult.

It should be noted that a minority of the participants pointed out characteristics pertaining to the artefact, such as aesthetics and texture, as possessing a desirable emotional quality, thus eliciting positive emotions. The significance of this point is that while certain attributes are integrated into the product

to elicit positive emotions from the customer, the same attributes may also elicit similar emotions from the workers who interact with the product throughout other life-phases. This is particularly the case when a product attribute does not interfere with the concerns of the worker. Unlike the product color, the texture of the artefact was considered to elicit positive emotions due to the fact that it did not influence in any negative manner the execution of the required tasks.

CONCLUSION

For many years, research into product design and emotion has in most part focused on the notion that emotions are elicited from the human customer as he/she interacts with the designed product during the use phase. The research work presented in this paper extends this idea by taking into account the numerous interactions, involving the human worker, which occur throughout different phases in the life of an artefact. The state-of-the-art literature suggests that the elicitation of emotions from human workers can in fact have a significant influence on their behavior. Thus it would be appropriate if the design of a product could contribute in the elicitation of the desired emotions from both the customer and the life-phase worker.

The main contribution of this paper is in the provision of a theoretical model (HELCI), which portrays human emotions as a consequence of interactions, which occur across the various phases in the life of a product. These interactions involve the human worker, the artefact in its various states, and a number of life-phase systems. The HELCI model provides a basis for understanding the emotions, which stem from each interaction. This is due to the fact that at its core, HELCI links the characteristics of the artefact, and other life-phase systems, with the emotions that are elicited as a consequence of life-phase interactions.

This underlying principle of HELCI has been demonstrated through the results obtained from an investigation into worker emotions within a manufacturing company. The study identified characteristics which were considered to elicit worker emotions. The human emotions were elicited as a result of the appraisal of stimuli in relation to the concerns of the worker. It follows that the reason why particular characteristics can elicit emotions is that these can facilitate or interfere with the execution of the expected tasks. The investigation also shows that while certain design decisions, related to the product characteristics, are made in order to elicit positive emotions from the end customer, the same characteristics can elicit significantly different emotions from the worker.

Although this work has focused on human emotions in the manufacturing phase, the results indicate the need to carry out further research by considering interactions involving the human worker across other life-cycle phases of the artefact. A limitation of the research presented in this paper was the small number of workers who participated in the investigation. Apart from a larger sample size, it is deemed necessary to conduct additional semi-structured interviews among workers who are concerned with the execution of a diversity of tasks that are not necessarily limited to visual inspection.

The intent of this research in the near future will be to exploit the gathered knowledge by implementing a CAD tool. The starting point in the development of such a CAD tool is the HELCI model. To this extent the HELCI model provides the basis for the structuring and for rendering explicit knowledge related to the emotions elicited from human life-phase workers. The CAD tool could be implemented in order to support the design of products which can elicit the desired emotions through the interactions which occur across various phases in the life-cycle of the artefact. This will provide industry with a means of reducing the costs incurred as a consequence of negative emotions, which include counter-productive work behavior and an increase in absenteeism.

REFERENCES

Borg, J. C. (1999) *Design Synthesis For Multi-X - A Life-Cycle Consequence Knowledge Approach*. University of Strathclyde: CAD Centre.

Chang, K., and Lu, L. (2007) 'Characteristics of organizational culture, stressors and wellbeing', *The case of Taiwanese organizations*, 22, (6), pp.549-568.

Desmet, P. M. A. (2012) 'Faces of Product Pleasure : 25 Positive Emotions in Human-Product Interactions', *International Journal of Design*, 6, (2), pp.1-29.

Farrugia, P. J., Borg, J. C., Grima, C., and Fenech, O. C. (2008) 'Form Design For Emotion with a Cameraphone Based Tool', paper presented at 6th *Design and Emotion Conference - D&E'08*, Hong Kong, 6 - 9 October 2008.

Fenech, O. C., and Borg, J. C. (2006a) 'A Model of Human Sensations as a Basis for "Design for Product-Emotions"', paper presented at *Design Conference '06*, Dubrovnik, Croatia, 15 - 18 May 2006 .

Fenech, O. C., and Borg, J. C. (2006b). *Towards A Sensory Approach for Designing Pleasurable User-Product Experiences*, paper presented at 6th *NordDesign 2006 Conference*, Reykjavik, Iceland, 16-18 August 2006 .

Fenko, A., Schifferstein, H. N. J., and Hekkert, P. (2011) 'Noisy Products : Does Appearance Matter?', *International Journal of Design*, 5, (3), pp.77-87.

Fokkinga, S., and Desmet, P. (2012) 'Darker Shades of Joy : The Role of Negative Emotion in Rich Product Experiences', *Design Issues*, 28, (4), pp . 42-56

Fokkinga, S. F., and Desmet, P. M. A. (2013) 'Ten Ways to Design for Disgust , Sadness , and Other Enjoyments : A Design Approach to Enrich Product Experiences with Negative Emotions', *International Journal of Design*, 7, (1), pp.19-36.

Hubka, V., and Eder, W. E. (1988) *Theory of Technical Systems: A Total Concept Theory for Engineering Design*. London: Springer-Verlag.

Imtiaz, S., and Ahmad, S. (n.d.) 'Impact Of Stress On Employee Productivity, Performance And Turnover ; An Important Managerial Issue', *International Review of Business Research Papers*, 5., pp 468-477.

Jo, M. (1992) 'Servicescapes : The Impact of Physical Surroundings on Customers and Employees', *Journal of Marketing*, 56, (2), pp. 57-71.

Lazarus, R. (2006) *Stress and emotion: A new synthesis*. University of Pittsburgh: Springer Publishing Company.

Lazarus, R. S., and Folkman, S. (1984) *Stress, appraisal, and coping*. New York, USA: Springer Publishing Company.

Ludden, G. D. S., and Schifferstein, H. N. J. (2009) 'Should Mary Smell Like Biscuit ?', *International Journal of Design*, 3, (3), pp.1-12.

Michie, S. (2002) 'Causes and management of stress at work', *Occupational & Environmental Medicine*, 59, (1), pp. 67-72.

Olesen, J. (1992) *Concurrent Development in Manufacturing based on dispositional mechanisms*. Technical University Denmark (DTH): Technical University Denmark.

Qureshi, M. I., Iftikhar, M., and Abbas, S. G. (2013) 'Relationship Between Job Stress , Workload , Environment and Employees Turnover Intentions : What We Know , What Should We Know', *World Applied Sciences Journal*, 23, (6), pp.764-770.

Rahman, O. (2012) 'The Influence of Visual and Tactile Inputs on Denim Jeans Evaluation', *International Journal of Design*, 6, (1), pp.11-25.

Russell, J. A. (2003) 'Core Affect and the Psychological Construction of Emotion', *Psychological Review*, 110, (1), pp.145-172.

Russell, J. A. (2009) 'Emotion, core affect, and psychological construction', *Cognition & Emotion*, 23, (7), pp.1259-1283.

Scherer, K., Schror, A., and Johnstone, T. (2001) 'Appraisal processes in emotion', *Handbook of affective sciences*. Canary: Oxford University Press, pp. 20-140.

Spector, P. E., and Fox, S. (2002) 'An emotion-centered model of voluntary work behavior', *Human Resource Management Review*, 12, (2), pp.269-292.

Yang, J., and Diefendorff, J. (2009) 'The relations of daily counterproductive workplace behavior with emotions, situational antecedents, and personality moderators: A diary study in Hong Kong', *Personnel Psychology*, 62, (2), pp.259-295.